

Evaluating the effectiveness of the national elderly care program in Oman: A cross-sectional study

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Abstract

Introduction: The aging population presents significant challenges to healthcare systems globally. In Oman, the National Program for Elderly Care (ECP) aims to address these challenges by providing comprehensive services through the primary healthcare (PHC) system. This study evaluates the effectiveness of Oman's PHC system in meeting the needs of citizens aged 60 years and older.

Methods: This descriptive study utilized national data from the PHC Information System, analyzing records of 17,243 Omani citizens aged 60 years and above enrolled in 2023. The study assessed program coverage, referral patterns, health condition prevalence, functional status, and registration dynamics using descriptive statistics and visualizations.

Results: The study found that 35% of the target elderly population was enrolled in the program nationwide, with significant regional variations. Al Dhahirah governorate had the highest enrollment (86%), while Muscat and Al Wusta had the lowest (<10%). Health institutions were the primary source of referrals (81% for females, 86% for males). The prevalence of chronic conditions such as diabetes and hypertension varied widely across governorates. Most elderly individuals were classified as independent/active, although a significant proportion required varying levels of support.

Conclusions: The ECP in Oman shows both successes and challenges. While some regions demonstrate effective outreach and high service utilization, others face significant barriers, leading to disparities in coverage and health outcomes. To enhance the program's effectiveness, targeted interventions, improved outreach in underserved areas, and continuous monitoring are recommended. Future research should include longitudinal and qualitative studies to further refine the care strategies for elderly people in Oman.

Take-home message: Oman's National Program for Elderly Care shows progress but faces regional disparities. Targeted interventions and better outreach are needed to improve coverage and ensure equitable care for the aging population.

Keywords: Aging population; elderly care; health disparities; Oman; primary healthcare.

INTRODUCTION

Globally, a significant demographic shift is characterized by increasing life expectancy and declining fertility rates, particularly in low-to-middle-income countries [1]. This phenomenon is causing a significant increase in the elderly population. Individuals aged 80 and above are expected to increase dramatically, from 126.5 million in 2015 to 446.6 million by 2050. This demographic trend presents considerable challenges to healthcare systems worldwide [2, 3]. The increased life expectancy is associated with a higher prevalence of chronic conditions and age-related disabilities, such as respiratory disorders, diabetes, sensory and cognitive impairments, and physical injuries. Variations in lifespan and access to healthcare resources across different nations influence the incidence of these conditions [4–6]. The increasing elderly population, particularly those aged 80 and above, calls for a thoroughly planned long-term healthcare service delivery system to facilitate the pronounced impact on the elderly due to their extended lifespans [7–11].

The World Health Organization (WHO) advocates "healthy aging," which is defined as maintaining the functional ability that enables an individual's well-being throughout their lifespan. The WHO's Public Health Framework (PHF) on Healthy Aging emphasizes the importance of preserving both intrinsic and functional capabilities to effectively address the challenges posed by an aging global population [12–14].

Oman, with a national population of 3,476,382 in 2023, includes 166,464 individuals aged 60 and above, representing 4.79% of the Omani population. By 2040, projections indicate that the number of elderly people in Oman will rise to 376,716, accounting for 11.80% of the population [15, 16]. To address the healthcare needs of this demographic, the Ministry of Health (MOH) has implemented the National Program for Elderly Care [17]. The MOH in Oman administers a comprehensive PHC system across 11 governorates (Al Dakhliyah, Al Dhahirah, Al Buraymi, Al Wusta, Dhofar, Musandam, Muscat, North Al Batinah, North Ash Sharqiyah, South Al Batinah, and South Ash Sharqiyah), which includes 192 PHCs, 21 extended centers, and 50 hospitals [18]. These healthcare facilities act as the initial point of contact for elderly patients, providing a wide range of services, including curative and preventive care. The system, which offers free services to citizens and affordable options for non-citizens, aims to promote equal access to healthcare, self-reliance, and community participation [19, 20].

The Elderly Care Program (ECP) in Oman, initiated in Al Dhakhalia in 2003 and implemented nationwide across Primary Healthcare Centers (PHCs) in 2011, has demonstrated several positive outcomes, which justified its expansion [40]. Cost-effectiveness was a crucial factor in its success. A 2007 cost analysis revealed that community health care services were significantly more economical compared to tertiary and secondary care. For instance, a single patient visit by a community health nurse costs approximately 3.620 Omani Rials (USD 9.5), in stark contrast to the 50–75 Omani Rials (USD 130–180) for a day's

stay in a tertiary-level hospital. This considerable cost savings was a strong motivator for the program's nationwide implementation [41]. The ECP's focus on community-based interventions aligns with global healthcare trends, which have been shifting towards preventive rather than curative care. This aligns with international best practices and strengthens the case for the program's expansion. Furthermore, Oman's changing demographics, including a rapidly growing and aging population and an increase in lifestyle-related chronic diseases, prompted the strategic development of the ECP. By proactively addressing these emerging health challenges, the program demonstrated its long-term value to the nation's healthcare system. A key strength of the ECP was its integration into the existing primary healthcare (PHC) structure. Rather than creating an independent service, this approach reinforced and enhanced the current system, leading to a more efficient and cost-effective use of resources [40].

The program, in partnership with the Ministry of Social Development (MOSD), focuses on the medical and social needs of the elderly, referring relevant cases to MOSD's social workers [17, 40]. To ensure targeted care, each PHC establishes an annual target group of elderly patients in January each year, based on updated data from the National Center for Statistics and Information (NCSI). Comprehensive assessments are a cornerstone of the ECP, encompassing socioeconomic, physical, and psychological aspects [24-37]. During the initial visit, healthcare providers use various tools, such as the Mini-Mental State Examination (MMSE) [22, 23], the Geriatric Depression Scale, and pressure ulcer risk assessment using the Braden Scale [38], to evaluate the patient's condition. Every six months, healthcare providers schedule follow-up visits for vital checks and blood sugar monitoring and conduct annual comprehensive geriatric assessments to ensure timely interventions and optimized care [17, 21].

The ECP employs a multi-dimensional approach, integrating assessments of cognitive function, socioeconomic context, functional independence, mental health, and nutritional status. These assessments contribute to an overall score that helps classify the patient's level of function and guides appropriate interventions [39].

While the ECP's comprehensive design holds promise, it is important to evaluate its effectiveness and identify potential areas for improvement. This study seeks to evaluate the effectiveness of Oman's PHC system in addressing the healthcare needs of citizens aged 60 years and older, with a focus on program coverage, health outcomes, functional status, and regional disparities. By identifying strengths and areas for improvement, the study aims to provide evidence-based recommendations for refining the ECP and enhancing the quality of life for Oman's aging population.

METHODS

Study setting, design, and procedures

Oman is situated on the southeastern coast of the Arabian Peninsula. It shares land borders with Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, and Yemen while having maritime borders with Iran and Pakistan.

A review study incorporated existing data from the MOH's Shifa 3+ Electronic Health System. The study population comprised all elderly citizens aged 60 and above enrolled in the National Program for Elderly Care from January 1, 2023 to December 31, 2023. We retrieved data using an intranet-based interface of the Shifa 3+ system, a Ministry of Health (MOH) system.

Study sampling and data collection

In each governorate of Oman, elderly care nurses play a pivotal role in data collection. They meticulously compile monthly reports on their patients, encompassing comprehensive information on various aspects of health and well-being. These reports are then automatically generated by the Shifa+ system, which serves as a nationwide repository for elderly care data.

This aggregated data provides a holistic view of the program's reach, referral patterns, prevalent health conditions, and the functional status of the elderly population across Oman. The compiled reports and dashboards are then thoroughly reviewed and analyzed by supervisors of the elderly care and community health services program at the central headquarters.

This analysis is crucial for assessing the program's effectiveness, identifying emerging trends, and making informed decisions regarding resource allocation and service enhancements.

It is important to note that this research relied exclusively on existing Electronic Health Records (EHRs) from the Shifa 3+ system, without using any specialized sample collection or laboratory evaluation protocols. The focus was on extracting relevant information related to program reach, referral patterns, health conditions, and the functional status of the elderly population.

Statistical analysis

To ensure accuracy and consistency, the collected data were rigorously reviewed to remove duplication and prepare for analysis. The data were then visualized and analyzed using Looker Studio (formerly Google Data Studio), generating interactive dashboards and comprehensive reports.

The analysis of results involved the utilization of various graphical and tabular representations to effectively depict the data. Graphs were employed to visually represent the distribution and comparison of data points, including target population achievements across different governorates, frequencies of various types of visits, proportions of referrals by source, and the prevalence of health conditions among elderly individuals. The rate of returning patients was calculated by expressing the number of follow-up visits as a percentage of the total number of visits (including both first visits and follow-up visits) for each gender and governorate. Similarly, the proportion of referrals by source for each gender was calculated to illustrate the relative contribution of each referral source (Self-Referral, Community Referral, and Health Institution Referral) to the total referrals.

Tables were used to present numerical data in a structured manner, highlighting the total number of visits, gender percentage distribution, sex ratio, correlations between referral types, and specific details on patient numbers and health conditions. Descriptive statistics were employed to summarize and interpret the data, with percentages, ratios, and averages calculated to highlight key findings and trends. The results were presented clearly and concisely, emphasizing the most relevant insights for each section of the analysis.

Ethical aspects

Anonymized data were used in this study, so ethical study approval was not required. The study was based on incorporated existing data from the Shifa 3+ Electronic Health System operated by the Ministry of Health (MOH). The data collection and analysis processes adhered to the privacy and confidentiality regulations governing the use of patient information within the Oman MOH. The study complies with the internal institutional review board's guidelines and adheres to the Declaration of Helsinki's principles.

RESULTS

Program coverage and enrollment

The enrollment data for the National Program for Elderly Care (ECP) show significant regional disparities across Oman. Of the 49,023 targeted elderly individuals, only 17,243 (35%) were enrolled nationwide. Table 1 presents a detailed breakdown of enrollment rates by governorate, highlighting the stark contrasts in coverage. For instance, Al Dhahirah achieved the highest enrollment rate at 86%, whereas Al Wusta and Muscat had the lowest rates below 10%.

Table 1. Enrollment rates by governorate.

	Target Population	Enrolled Population	Enrollment Percentage
Ad Dakhliyah	5687	1566	28%
Ad Dhahirah	3439	2970	86%
Al Buraymi	1073	887	83%

	Target Population	Enrolled Population	Enrollment Percentage
Al Wusta	1496	139	9%
Dhofar	6502	1870	29%
Musandam	569	126	22%
Muscat	10722	1016	9%
North Al Batinah	8396	4531	54%
North Ash Sharqiyah	3062	1439	47%
South Al Batinah	5483	1623	30%
South Ash Sharqiyah	3660	1076	29%

Note: Enrollment percentages above 50% are considered high, between 30%-50% are medium, and below 30% are low.

Figure 1 visually represents these regional differences, making comparing enrollment rates across the governorates easier. North Al Batinah, with 4,531 enrolled elderly, recorded the highest number of initial visits, indicating its pivotal role as a healthcare access point.

Figure 1. Distribution of Target Population Achievement Across Different Governorates in Oman for the Elderly Care Program (2023).

Referral patterns

As illustrated in Table 2, referral patterns indicate that health institutions are the primary referral source, contributing 81% of female and 86% of male referrals.

Table 2. Referral sources by governorate and gender.

Governorate	Self-Refer- ral (%) (M)	Self-Refer- ral (%) (F)	Commu- nity Referral (%) (M)	Community Referral (%) (F)	Health Institution (%) (M)	Health In- stitution (%) (F)	Total
Al Dakhliyah	12 (1%)	19 (1%)	29 (2%)	44 (3%)	622 (48%)	999 (52%)	1725
Al Dhahirah	91 (3%)	120 (4%)	31 (1%)	43 (2%)	988 (36%)	1,460 (64%)	2733
Al Buraymi	27 (3%)	30 (2%)	35 (4%)	27 (2%)	411 (44%)	403 (56%)	933

Governorate	Self-Referral (%) (M)	Self-Referral (%) (F)	Community Referral (%) (M)	Community Referral (%) (F)	Health Institution (%) (M)	Health Institution (%) (F)	Total
Al Wusta	0 (0%)	6 (5%)	25 (24%)	28 (27%)	27 (26%)	19 (74%)	105
Dhofar	30 (2%)	31 (1%)	41 (2%)	65 (4%)	823 (45%)	839 (55%)	1829
Musandam	6 (4%)	1 (1%)	12 (8%)	17 (12%)	53 (37%)	53 (63%)	142
Muscat	29 (4%)	31 (1%)	1 (<1%)	7 (1%)	303 (37%)	445 (63%)	816
North Al Batinah	164 (4%)	169 (4%)	157 (4%)	203 (5%)	1,526 (36%)	1,994 (64%)	4213
North Ash Sharqiyah	26 (2%)	49 (3%)	2 (<1%)	7 (0%)	624 (43%)	743 (57%)	1451
South Al Batinah	73 (3%)	626 (29%)	48 (2%)	56 (3%)	512 (24%)	813 (76%)	2128
South Ash Sharqiyah	168 (16%)	241 (11%)	32 (3%)	47 (4%)	267 (25%)	329 (75%)	1084
Total	626 (9%)	1,323 (13%)	413 (6%)	544 (6%)	6,156 (86%)	8,097 (81%)	

Note: High self-referral percentages indicate better community awareness and engagement, while high health institution referrals suggest reliance on institutional healthcare.

Self-referrals accounted for 13% among females and 9% among males, while community referrals were uniformly 6% for both genders. North Al Batinah again led in total referrals with 4,213, as shown in Table 2 and Figure 2. Conversely, Al Wusta had the lowest referral count at 105. These figures suggest potential barriers in self and community referrals, possibly due to limited awareness or transportation challenges, particularly in regions with lower referral rates.

Figure 2. Distribution and Frequency of Different Types of Visits by Gender Across Governorates in Oman (2023).

Prevalence of health conditions

Figure 3 provides a detailed comparison of the prevalence of chronic conditions such as diabetes and hypertension. For example, diabetes prevalence during initial visits ranged from a low of 2% in Al Buraymi to a high of 16% in Al Wusta. Similarly, hypertension prevalence showed wide variation, ranging from 1% to 19%. These findings underline the need for tailored, region-specific healthcare interventions to manage chronic conditions in the elderly population effectively.

Figure 3. Prevalence of health conditions by governorate.

Functional status

The functional status of elderly individuals, categorized into independent, semi-independent, semi-dependent, and dependent/retired, also showed significant regional differences. As presented in Table 3 and visualized in Figure 4, 50% of males and 55% of females were classified as independent/active.

Table 3. Functional status by governorate.

Governorate	Independ-ent/ Active (M)	Independ-ent/ Active (F)	Semi-Independ-ent (M)	Semi-Inde-pendent (F)	Semi-Depend-ent (M)	Semi-Depend-ent (F)	Depend-ent/ Retired (M)	Depend-ent/ Retired (F)
Ad Dakhliyah	748	1104	49	113	16	27	41	11
Ad Dhahirah	992	1154	176	263	73	83	22	30
Al Buraymi	433	470	37	54	24	29	6	8
Al Wusta	906	818	24	39	5	86	14	38
Dhofar	918	829	156	201	28	68	10	67
Musandam	39	24	17	17	5	5	2	2
Muscat	434	339	51	28	12	9	15	3

Governorate	Independent/Active (M)	Independent/Active (F)	Semi-Independent (M)	Semi-Independent (F)	Semi-Dependent (M)	Semi-Dependent (F)	Dependent/Retired (M)	Dependent/Retired (F)
North Al Batinah	1373	1608	241	381	94	135	69	102
North Ash Sharqiyah	587	726	17	17	14	10	4	2
South Al Batinah	508	705	55	92	26	35	14	28
South Ash Sharqiyah	1752	1739	328	413	131	159	76	203

Note: Functional status categories reflect the level of independence among the elderly, which is crucial for tailoring appropriate healthcare interventions.

Figure 4. Elderly Functional Status by Governorate

However, Al Wusta governorate exhibited a higher proportion of semi-dependent and dependent individuals, highlighting the need for enhanced support services in these areas. Semi-independent individuals comprised 7% of males and 9% of females, while 2% of males and 4% of females were semi-dependent. The dependent/retired category accounted for 2% of males and 3% of females.

Mortality and registration dynamics

Mortality rates and registration dynamics are crucial for understanding the ongoing engagement with the ECP. As shown in Table 4, 3% of the elderly population registered in the program died in 2023, with a slightly higher mortality rate among males (553 deaths) compared to females (534 deaths).

Table 4. Mortality and registration dynamics by governorate.

Governorate	Deaths (M)	Deaths (F)	New Registrations (M)	New Registrations (F)	Removals (M)	Removals (F)	Total Registered (M)	Total Registered (F)
Al Dakhliyah	83 (5%)	125 (8%)	610 (39%)	931 (59%)	424 (27%)	681 (43%)	9,955	12,430
Al Dhahirah	62 (2%)	69 (2%)	1,188 (40%)	1,507 (51%)	173 (6%)	246 (8%)	2,897	1,666
Al Buraymi	9 (1%)	15 (2%)	439 (50%)	426 (48%)	23 (3%)	29 (3%)	2,647	2,659
Al Wusta	7 (5%)	6 (4%)	63 (45%)	53 (38%)	18 (13%)	8 (6%)	587	407
Dhofar	44 (2%)	20 (1%)	883 (47%)	881 (47%)	141 (8%)	194 (10%)	3,546	3,494
Musandam	6 (5%)	4 (3%)	285 (226%)	79 (63%)	3 (2%)	3 (2%)	1,835	1,290
Muscat	16 (2%)	6 (1%)	505 (50%)	437 (43%)	25 (2%)	8 (1%)	2,930	2,405
North Al Batinah	79 (2%)	61 (1%)	1,719 (38%)	2,175 (48%)	127 (3%)	123 (3%)	15,554	16,367
North Ash Sharqiyah	89 (6%)	73 (5%)	674 (47%)	811 (56%)	113 (8%)	108 (8%)	4,755	5,969
South Al Batinah	57 (4%)	68 (4%)	516 (32%)	750 (46%)	58 (4%)	86 (5%)	7,817	8,908
South Ash Sharqiyah	94 (9%)	87 (8%)	367 (34%)	514 (48%)	129 (12%)	100 (9%)	5,927	5,689
Overall	553 (3%)	534 (3%)	9,029 (52%)	9,765 (57%)	1,234 (7%)	1,586 (9%)	58,450	61,284

Note: Mortality and registration dynamics are important for understanding the turnover and sustainability of the elderly care program in each region.

South Ash Sharqiyah governorate had a notably higher mortality rate among registered males (9%). Figure 5 illustrates the registration dynamics, showing that 52% of the total male and 57% of the female population were newly registered during the year, reflecting ongoing engagement with the program. However, significant removals from the register, particularly in Al Wusta and South Ash Sharqiyah, indicated possible retention or data management issues.

Figure 5. Mortality and registration dynamics by governorate.

Summary

The results highlight both successes and ongoing challenges within the ECP. Despite high engagement in some regions, significant disparities in program coverage, health outcomes, and functional status must be addressed. Figures and tables provided throughout this section offer a clear and detailed representation of these findings, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions, especially in underserved areas. Continuous monitoring and strategic regional capacity building are essential for improving the program's effectiveness and ensuring equitable healthcare access for all elderly individuals in Oman.

DISCUSSION

The evaluation of Oman's National Elderly Care Program (ECP) in 2023 reveals a nuanced landscape of healthcare delivery to the aging population, marked by significant successes and critical challenges. This study underscores the importance of regional customization of healthcare services to address the diverse needs of the elderly across different governorates.

A key finding of the study is the substantial regional disparities in program coverage. While governorates such as Al Dhahirah reported high enrollment rates of up to 86%, others, including Al Wusta and Muscat, exhibited much lower rates, below 10%. These disparities highlight the influence of geographical, infrastructural, and potentially cultural factors on the accessibility and uptake of elderly care services. The high coverage in some regions suggests that effective integration of the program into the local healthcare system, coupled with sufficient resources, can significantly enhance reach. Conversely, the low coverage in other regions points to the need for targeted outreach and educational initiatives, particularly in underserved areas where barriers to access may include transportation challenges, lack of awareness, or inadequate local healthcare infrastructure [2,4].

The study reveals a strong reliance on institutional healthcare pathways, with health institutions serving as the primary source of referrals, contributing to 81% of female and 86% of male referrals. This reliance indicates potential gaps in community engagement and preventive care initiatives, as evidenced by the low rates of self-referrals and community referrals. To enhance the program's overall effectiveness, it is crucial to strengthen community-based health education and support systems, thereby empowering the elderly and their families to seek care [6,8] proactively.

There are significant regional variations in the prevalence of chronic health conditions, such as diabetes and hypertension. For instance, diabetes prevalence ranged from 2% in Al Buraymi to 16% in Al Wusta, illustrating the need for region-specific healthcare strategies tailored to address the unique health challenges faced by elderly populations in different areas. Furthermore, the data on functional status reveal that while most elderly individuals are classified as independent or active, a considerable proportion requires varying levels of support, particularly in regions like Al Wusta. This underscores the importance of providing comprehensive support services, including home-based care, assistive devices, and caregiver support, to improve the quality of life for elderly individuals with functional limitations [7,11].

The study's analysis of registration dynamics shows ongoing engagement with the ECP, as indicated by the high number of new registrations. However, significant numbers of removals from the register, particularly in regions like South Ash Sharqiyah and Al Wusta, where mortality rates are higher, suggest underlying issues such as late presentation of health conditions, inadequate management of chronic diseases, or broader socio-economic factors affecting the elderly population. Continuous monitoring of these trends is essential for understanding and addressing the factors contributing to high mortality and dropout rates from the program [9,13].

Strengths and limitations of the study

This study's primary strength lies in its comprehensive analysis of the National Elderly Care Program across multiple governorates in Oman. It provides a detailed overview of regional healthcare access, utilization, and outcomes disparities. The use of extensive national data allows for a robust examination of the program's effectiveness in addressing the healthcare needs of the elderly population. Additionally, the study highlights critical areas for improvement, offering actionable insights for policy-makers and healthcare providers. However, the study is not without limitations. The reliance on existing electronic health

records and manual data entry introduces the possibility of data inaccuracies and biases. Furthermore, the study's retrospective design limits the ability to establish causality between program interventions and health outcomes. The focus on enrolled citizens may also limit the generalizability of the findings to the broader elderly population, particularly those not engaged with the healthcare system. Lastly, the absence of qualitative data restricts a deeper understanding of the individual experiences and challenges within the program, which could provide valuable context to the quantitative findings.

Implications for future research and policy

The findings of this study have important implications for future research and policy development. There is a clear need for longitudinal studies that track the long-term health outcomes of elderly individuals enrolled in the ECP. Such studies could provide valuable insights into the program's effectiveness over time and help identify areas where interventions can be optimized. Additionally, qualitative research focusing on the experiences and challenges faced by elderly individuals and their caregivers could provide a deeper understanding of the barriers to accessing care and inform the development of more user-centered healthcare services [14,18].

From a policy perspective, enhancing regional capacity and tailoring healthcare strategies to meet the specific needs of different governorates is essential for improving the program's overall effectiveness. This includes investing in community health initiatives, improving transportation infrastructure to facilitate access to healthcare facilities, and ensuring that healthcare providers are trained to address the unique needs of the elderly [19,21].

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, while Oman's National Elderly Care Program has achieved significant success in certain regions, substantial disparities in coverage, health outcomes, and functional status require attention. Targeted interventions, enhanced community engagement, and continuous monitoring are essential to ensure that the program effectively meets the diverse and evolving needs of Oman's aging population. Future research and policy efforts should focus on addressing the identified gaps to promote healthy aging and improve the quality of life for the elderly across all regions of Oman.

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References

1. Bongaarts J. Human population growth and the demographic transition. *Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci.* 2009;364(1532):2985-2990.
2. World Health Organization. Ageing and health. WHO; 2022. <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/ageing-and-health>. Accessed 10 July 2024.
3. US Census Bureau. U.S. Older Population Grew From 2010 to 2020 at Fastest Rate Since 1880 to 1890. *Census.gov*; 2023. <https://www.census.gov/library/stories/2023/05/2020-census-united-states-older-population-grew.html>. Accessed 10 July 2024.
4. Laditka JN, Laditka SB. Associations of multiple chronic health conditions with active life expectancy in the United States. *Disabil Rehabil.* 2015;38(4):354-361.

5. Lourida I, Bennett HQ, Beyer F, Thompson-Coon J, Llewellyn DJ, Hill KD, et al. The impact of long-term conditions on disability-free life expectancy: A systematic review. *PLOS Glob Public Health*. 2022;2(8).
6. Galvin AE, Friedman DB, Hébert JR, Bond SM, Grace A, Salerno M, et al. Focus on disability-free life expectancy: Implications for health-related quality of life. *Qual Life Res*. 2021;30(8):2187-2195.
7. Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development. Preventing Ageing Unequally. OECD; 2017. https://read.oecd-ilibrary.org/employment/preventing-ageing-unequally_9789264279087-en#page15. Accessed 10 July 2024.
8. Jones CH, Dolsten M. Healthcare on the brink: navigating the challenges of an aging society in the United States. *NPJ Aging*. 2024;10(1).
9. European Commission. Projected growth in demand for long-term care services represents a major challenge for ageing Europe. Knowledge for Policy; 2022. https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/news/projected-growth-demand-long-term-care-services-represents-major-challenge-ageing-europe_en. Accessed 10 July 2024.
10. National Academies Press (US). Health Status and Health Care Service Utilization. NIH.gov; 2020. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK215400/>. Accessed 10 July 2024.
11. Ostan R, Monti D, Guerresi P, Bussolotto M, Franceschi C, Baggio G. Gender, aging and longevity in humans: An update of an intriguing/neglected scenario paving the way to a gender-specific medicine. *Clin Sci (Lond)*. 2016;130(19):1711-1725.
12. Rudnicka E, Napierala P, Podfigurna A, Męczekalski B, Smolarczyk R, Grymowicz M. The World Health Organization (WHO) approach to healthy ageing. *Maturitas*. 2020;139:6-11.
13. Nestola T, Cesari M. WHO Approach to Healthy Aging. In: Cesari M, editor. *Encyclopedia of Gerontology and Population Aging*. Springer; 2022. p. 1-21. https://link.springer.com/referenceworkentry/10.1007/978-3-030-01782-8_105-1. Accessed 10 July 2024.
14. World Health Organization. Key terms: Healthy Ageing. WHO; 2019. https://www.who.int/docs/default-source/documents/decade-of-health-ageing/decade-healthy-ageing-update-march-2019.pdf?sfvrsn=5a6d0e5c_2. Accessed 10 July 2024.
15. eCensus Portal. *Ecensus.gov.om*; 2020. <https://ecensus.gov.om/ecen-portal/indicators/category/1/subCategory/6>. Accessed 10 July 2024.
16. National Center for Statistics and Information. The expected number of societal categories in Oman at 2040 will reach 1.5 million children, 2 million women, and 376.7 thousand elderly people. *Ncsi.gov.om*; 2024. https://www.ncsi.gov.om/News/Pages/NewsCT_20240122145912284.aspx. Accessed 10 July 2024.
17. Al Rashidi B, Alwahaibi A, Al Awaity S. Integrated Care for the Elderly in the Primary Health Care setting Oman: The Scope and Experience. *Res Gate*; 2022. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/358703967_Integrated_Care_for_the_Elderly_in_the_Primary_Health_Care_setting_Oman_The_Scope_and_Experience. Accessed 10 July 2024.
18. Ministry of Health. Annual Health Report 2020. Oman: Ministry of Health; 2020. https://www.moh.gov.om/en/web/statistics/annual-reports/-/asset_publisher/aQdmeIpTn5pS/content/-2-22?inheritRedirect=false&redirect=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.moh.gov.om%2Fen%2Fweb%2Fstatistics%2Fannual-reports%3Fp_p_id%3D101_IN-STANCE_aQdmeIpTn5pS%26p_p_lifecycle%3D0%26p_p_state%3Dnormal%26p_p_mode%3Dview%26p_p_col_id%3Dcolumn-2%26p_p_col_count%3D1. Accessed 10 July 2024.
19. World Health Organization. Country Cooperation Strategy for WHO and Oman. WHO; 2010. https://applications.emro.who.int/docs/CCS_Oman_2010_EN_14485.pdf. Accessed 10 July 2024.
20. Ministry of Health. Resources. Oman: Ministry of Health; 2019. <https://www.moh.gov.om/en/web/directorate-general-of-planning/re-sources>. Accessed 10 July 2024.
21. Ministry of Health. Other services. Oman: Ministry of Health; 2024. <https://www.moh.gov.om/en/web/directorate-general-health-services-dhahira/services>. Accessed 10 July 2024.
22. Gallegos M, Morgan ML, Cervigni M, Peixoto JG, Da Silva TM, Nascimento MP, et al. 45 Years of the mini-mental state examination (MMSE): A perspective from Ibero-America. *Dement Neuropsychol*. 2022;16(4):384-387.
23. Folstein MF, Folstein SE, McHugh PR. "Mini-mental state." *J Psychiatr Res*. 1975;12(3):189-198.

24. Nikolaus T, Specht-Leible N, Bach M, Schlierf G, Oster P, Schumacher M. A randomized trial of comprehensive geriatric assessment and home intervention in the care of hospitalized patients. *Age Ageing*. 1999;28(6):543-550.
25. Welsh TJ, Gordon AL, Gladman JR, Hosking D, May CR, Dyas JV. Comprehensive geriatric assessment – a guide for the non-specialist. *Int J Clin Pract*. 2014;68(3):290-293.
26. British Geriatric Society. Comprehensive Geriatric Assessment Toolkit for Primary Care Practitioners. British Geriatric Society; 2019. Available from: https://www.bgs.org.uk/sites/default/files/content/resources/files/2019-02-08/BGS%20Toolkit%20-%20FINAL%20FOR%20WEB_0.pdf. Accessed 10 July 2024.
27. Kudelka J, Ollenschläger M, Dodel R, Konrad R, Meyer H, Ziesenis A, et al. Which Comprehensive Geriatric Assessment (CGA) instruments are currently used in Germany: A survey. *BMC Geriatr*. 2024;24(1):15.
28. Nikolaus T. [Social aspects in diagnosis and therapy of very elderly patients. Initial experiences with a newly developed questionnaire within the scope of geriatric assessment]. *Z Gerontol Geriatr*. 1994;27(4):262-267.
29. Edemekong PF, Bomgaars DL, Sukumaran S, Levy SB. Activities of Daily Living. *StatPearls* [Internet]. 2023. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK470404/#:~:text=The%20activities%20of%20daily%20living%20are%20classified%20into%20basic%20ADLs,transferring%20or%20ambulating%2C%20and%20eating>. Accessed 10 July 2024.
30. Edemekong PF, Bomgaars DL, Sukumaran S, Schoo C. Activities of Daily Living. 2023 Jun 26. In: *StatPearls* [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2024 Jan.
31. Ellis G, Gardner M, Tsiachristas A, Langhorne P, Burke O, Harwood RH, et al. Comprehensive geriatric assessment for older adults admitted to hospital. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2017;(9).
32. National Clinical Programme for Older People. Comprehensive Geriatric Assessment: A Summary Adapted from Specialist Geriatric Team Guidance on Comprehensive Geriatric Assessment National Clinical Programme for Older People (2016). Health Service Executive; 2016. <https://www.hse.ie/eng/services/publications/clinical-strategy-and-programmes/comprehensive-geriatric-assessment-summary.pdf>
33. British Geriatric Society. Comprehensive Geriatric Assessment Toolkit for Primary Care Practitioners. British Geriatric Society; 2019. https://www.bgs.org.uk/sites/default/files/content/resources/files/2019-02-08/BGS%20Toolkit%20-%20FINAL%20FOR%20WEB_0.pdf. Accessed 10 July 2024.
34. Mann E, Koller M, Mann C, van der Cammen TJM, Steurer J, Puhan MA, et al. Comprehensive Geriatric Assessment (CGA) in general practice: Results from a pilot study in Vorarlberg, Austria. *BMC Geriatr*. 2004;4(1):4.
35. Asante D, McLachlan CS, Pickles D, Booth K, Cowin L, Anderson J, et al. Understanding Unmet Care Needs of Rural Older Adults with Chronic Health Conditions: A Qualitative Study. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2023;20(4):3298.
36. Mathis A, Rooks RN, Wiltshire J, Apodaca C, McClellan M, Knopf NA, et al. Use of Health Information Varies by Region Among Older Adults in the U.S. *Gerontol Geriatr Med*. 2021;7:2333721421997198.
37. McMaughan DJ, Oloruntoba O, Smith ML, Smith JR, Jones R, Ory MG, et al. Socioeconomic Status and Access to Healthcare: Interrelated Drivers for Healthy Aging. *Front Public Health*. 2020;8:231.
38. Kennerly SM, Sharkey PD, Horn SD, Smout RJ, Swoboda J, Berlowitz DR, et al. Nursing Assessment of Pressure Injury Risk with the Braden Scale Validated against Sensor-Based Measurement of Movement. *Healthcare (Basel)*. 2022;10(11):2330.
39. Ministry of Health. Resources. Oman: Ministry of Health; 2023. <https://www.moh.gov.om/en/web/general-directorate-of-primary-health-care/resources>. Accessed 10 July 2024.
40. Yassin O. Elderly Care Service Programme: 28 Steps from Vision to Service Provision an Experience from Oman (1st ed.). Oman: Ministry of Health, WHO; 2012.

